

SURVEY ON TECHNOLOGICAL PROTECTION MEASURES

Impacts for Researchers, Libraries & Archives

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Knowledge Rights 21 is focused on bringing about changes in legislation and practice across Europe that will strengthen the right of all to knowledge. It is built on a conviction that access to knowledge is essential for education, innovation and research, and that everyone in society should have the possibility to access and use information in both analogue and digital forms. This, in turn, will help Europe deliver on its economic, social, environmental and democratic potential.

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About the Three Reports:

This report is the second in a three-part series assessing the legal status and providing evidence on Technological Protection Measures (TPMs). Report 1 by Anthony Rosborough (2024) provides a comparative doctrinal analysis of TPMs in the 27 Member States of the European Union plus key comparator jurisdictions including the UK. That document contains a detailed analysis of the status of TPMs and different national approaches taken inside and outside of Europe to ensure access to works for beneficiaries of exceptions and limitations to copyright. Report 2 (this document) provides evidence on the effects of TPMs for researchers, libraries and archives, gathered from a survey of researchers and institutions. The results offer insight into specific impediments to research, education and preservation, as well as the outcomes of legal requests to rightsholders to provide access. Report 3 provides economic evidence of the costs of dealing with TPMs in the preservation of digital materials. Quantitative data are analysed from the MAME video game emulation project, revealing significant labour costs and missing use arising from the need to circumvent TPMs to preserve digital materials, an issue of relevance for a range of digital preservation and research contexts.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports on the results of a survey carried out to assess the impact of Technological Protection Measures (TPMs) on research, education and preservation in Europe (including the UK). In the context of legal ambiguity about the relationship between TPMs and exceptions to copyright, the results provide empirical data on current practices and needs of researchers and research support institutions such as libraries and archives. The survey was conducted with both individual researchers as well as institutions. We identify major impediments to the socially vital functions of research, education and preservation. Specific findings include:

- ▶ Institutions widely reported that TPMs inhibited their core functions of research, lending, learning and teaching, as well as other activities such as text-and-data mining and bibliometric scraping.
- ▶ 78% of researchers reported limits on downloading and 72% limits on access.
- ▶ TPMs were a major source of disutility for researchers, with 48% of institutions and 80% of individuals reporting they would avoid acquiring TPM-protected materials.
- ▶ Over 20% of institutions reported that TPMs inhibited accessibility, format shifting and preservation, uses ordinarily covered by copyright exceptions.
- ▶ Systems to request removal of TPMs are cumbersome, slow and under-utilised. Only 37% of institutions and 29% of individuals had made a formal request to a rightsholder to remove TPMs in order to benefit from an exception, with many reporting slow response times or no response at all.
- ▶ In 33% of cases where an individual researcher requested removal of TPMs by a publisher, the request was declined or no response was received.
- ▶ The amount of time from request from a library to a publisher response varied widely, with 11.3% of requests settled in under 2 days, 25.7% of requests taking up to a week, 31.7% of requests taking up to a month and 20% of requests taking over 1 month to resolve.
- ▶ The majority of libraries and researchers indicated that 72 hours or less was an acceptable wait time for a response from publishers, suggesting that the current situation in practice is not meeting expectations (Table 2).
- ▶ 59.6% of individual researchers encountered online access restrictions, reporting them to be a major impediment to research.
- ▶ Among institutions that experienced an account suspension, only 25.8% (9.8% of institutions) reported that the provider informed them an issue relating to TPMs had been corrected.
- ▶ Within the total sample of surveyed institutions 25% reported making a successful request to a rightsholder, while 4.3% were successful but only after agreeing to higher payment terms to enable access, and 8.7% made a request but were unsuccessful.
- ▶ In 8.4% of cases (3.2% of institutions), the institution decided to change to a different provider with more favourable access conditions. In the majority of suspensions (65.8% of cases, 25% of institutions) the institution changed their behaviour to comply with the access rules set by the provider in order to have access restored.

- ▶ Compared to individual researchers, institutions did not report feeling able to request refunds or switch between different providers in the market if they were unhappy with licence conditions or TPMs imposed by a provider.
- ▶ Individuals and institutions reported low confidence in their understanding of the law around TPMs and copyright exceptions, with lowest confidence among the smallest institutions.
- ▶ A prominent finding is that institutions had limited human and technical resources to assess legal options or to engage with publishers to request removal of TPMs, and this is borne out in the low rate of interaction with rightsholders or government administrative processes (see Figure 7).

Overall, we find that TPMs considerably inhibit activities otherwise permitted by exceptions to copyright such as research and preservation. On the institutional side, uncertainty about legal routes to accessing works, lack of resources and reputational considerations lead to an inability to make full lawful use of works protected by TPMs. Individual researchers reported more willingness to circumvent TPMs on their own in order to make otherwise lawful use of works, but expressed frustration that they could not always access materials through their research support institutions or other lawful access points, where TPMs prevented them from being able to carry out normally permitted acts such as education or research.

Based on the results of our survey we make the following recommendations:

- 1/** We support the proposals by the DG RTD (European Commission, 2024) including addition of all research-related copyright exceptions to the list in Article 6(4) InfoSoc Directive, such as the temporary copying exception in Article 5(1) and the quotation right in Article 5(3)(d), both of which may have research and education applications.
- 2/** We recommend adopting 72-hour time limits for responses from rightsholders to requests from beneficiaries of exceptions after which researchers should be legally able to seek other means of removing or circumventing TPMs.
- 3/** We recommend a more robust and transparent processing and reporting system that logs TPM access requests and provides publicly available data on outcomes. A particular emphasis should be placed on redressing equity gaps identified in this research (e.g. smaller institutions and researchers without institutional support). We recommend that policy take account of future social and economic costs of TPMs and weigh the significant social costs to research, innovation and the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms imposed by TPMs, to improve European research and innovation. Research, education and preservation are significant enablers of economic growth, and technological barriers to accessing information impact on the research-intensive sectors of our economy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Libraries and archives perform vital functions in our society: they support fundamental rights and societal progress by promoting science, education and research. They act as repositories of our collective knowledge, promoting community engagement and culture, as well as disseminating research as inputs to follow-on innovation. Although libraries and archives are legally empowered to carry out these important functions (research, education and preservation) their work can be impeded by copyright law.

Copyright's emphasis on enabling rightsholders to control access and dissemination of their work sometimes produces unintended impacts for researchers and institutions. For example, copyright law in many jurisdictions prohibits the circumvention of technological protection measures (TPMs) that control access to and copying of works. TPMs can interfere with socially beneficial and economically relevant uses including research and preservation, because they impact on a range of information used by researchers, libraries and archives, such as e-books and e-journals, audiovisual materials, video games, online databases and digital images.

Many jurisdictions have adopted provisions which prohibit circumvention or removal of TPMs. In the European Union, Article 6(1) of the Information Society Directive (2001/29) required Member States to introduce legal measures protecting TPMs. TPMs are broadly defined under the Directive as, "any technology, device or component that, in the normal course of its operation, is designed to prevent or restrict acts, in respect of works or other subject-matter, which are not authorised by the rightholder". Protection of TPMs includes prohibitions on the manufacture, sale, import, distribution and use of tools to circumvent TPMs, which inhibit researchers and institutions from accessing and using materials in the course of their work (Favale, 2011; McDonald et al., 2015; Renda et al., 2015). The interaction between exceptions to copyright and the protection of TPMs remains unclear and is rendered more ambiguous by different national implementations of the InfoSoc Directive (Rosborough, 2024). As stated by the European Commission (DG RTD) "EU copyright law does not require that technical conditions for access be designed in a way that gives researchers the opportunity to benefit from statutory research exceptions" (2024: 155). While article 6(4) of the Directive instructed Member States to "take appropriate measures to ensure that rightholders make available to the beneficiary of an exception or limitation provided for in national law ... the means of benefiting from that exception", this has taken different forms within the EU.

Some jurisdictions have established formal mechanisms enabling beneficiaries of copyright exceptions to request access to TPM-protected materials while other states do not provide a clear means of access. Libraries, archives and research support institutions would benefit from greater legal clarity about what they are permitted to do with works protected by TPMs. As would the students, researchers, members of the public, businesses, scientists, and others who depend on access to copyright materials to conduct their lawful and beneficial work. Given the ambiguous legal terrain, more precise data are needed to assess impact of TPMs on beneficiaries of exceptions and the uptake of formal processes to request removal where available. Our ambition with this study is to provide empirical evidence to support policy making and identify areas where the law concerning TPMs and copyright exceptions can be improved.

This report assesses the current situation for users (researchers, scientists, students, authors, businesses, etc.) as well as libraries and archives that deal with copyright TPMs in material they own or access. Our study considers both perspectives: institutions seeking to provide access, and importantly the researchers who use copyright materials. The aim of this study is to ascertain whether copyright TPMs prevent institutions and researchers from carrying out their public roles, and the scale of any challenges encountered. We adopt a survey method to capture the widest range of perspectives possible from the target population of research institutions and users in the European Union, plus the UK. To our knowledge, our survey is the most comprehensive to date carried out with libraries and archives on their experiences with TPMs.

The report is structured as follows: **Section 2** provides an overview of existing empirical literature on the impact of TPMs in research and preservation. **Section 3** outlines the survey method and design. **Section 4** details findings from the survey of library and archive institutions, while **Section 5** presents findings from the survey of individual researchers. **Section 6** provides policy recommendations, and **Section 7** describes limitations of the study and directions for future research. **Section 8** concludes the report. A full copy of the survey instrument is provided in **Annex 1**.

2. REVIEW OF EXISTING LITERATURE

There is relatively scant empirical data on the interaction between TPMs and research, education and preservation uses, with some notable exceptions that we discuss herein (Akester, 2009; Walters, 2013; Walters, 2014; Roncevic, 2020; Klein & Whyte, 2022; European Commission, 2024). One of the earliest comprehensive empirical studies of digital locks and TPMs was carried out by Akester (2009). That study examined whether DRM and TPMs were preventing librarians, visually impaired people, private users, lecturers, students and researchers from carrying out lawfully permitted acts, whether those users were able to resort to non-digital versions of TPM-protected materials, and what difficulties they encountered in accessing materials. Since that time there have been several other empirical studies, including a joint study carried out by the Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER) alongside the UK Libraries and Archives Copyright Alliance (LACA) in 2020, and a large-scale study on the impact of copyright on open knowledge in Europe carried out by the European Commission Directorate General for Research and Innovation in 2024, which included findings about the impact of TPMs. Our present study seeks to update and expand these existing studies, to assess whether challenges identified in the earlier empirical work persist, and to identify new challenges where they are emerging. In the section below, we review the existing empirical literature and discuss previous findings on the impact of DRM and TPMs for libraries and users.

2.1 LIBRARIES, ARCHIVES AND RESEARCH SUPPORT INSTITUTIONS

The research method adopted by Akester (2009) consisted of survey questionnaires and structured interviews conducted with a purposive sample of participants from various stakeholder groups, which included library professionals, visually impaired users, university lecturers, researchers and students. In regard to libraries and archives, Akester's findings suggested that TPMs were causing significant impediment to research, lending and preservation functions. Her respondents noted that licences imposed by publishers were often more restrictive than copyright law, preventing certain kinds of lawful uses such as making on-site archival copies of digital materials (2009: 36). Licence restrictions were also passed along to users who accessed material remotely. Remote users of digital materials often encountered stronger DRM protections than on-site users, such as "print once" limitations (2009: 37). DRM tied to specific technological standards or formats caused impediments for users, and put archival copies at risk, for example if a third-party DRM provider left the business (2009: 38). The advent of software-as-a-service (SaaS) business models was noted as an area of concern, especially for "born-digital" archival content that depended on legacy IT devices and operating systems to be accessed.¹

¹ For more on digital preservation, see Report 3 by Erickson and Rodriguez Perez (2024) Technological Protection Measures and Digital Preservation: Evidence from Video Games. Knowledge Rights 21 Report. DOI - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14165368>

According to one respondent from the British Library, “works in digital format do not stand alone, requiring considerable support infrastructure (in the form of hardware and software) to be usable and there are concerns as to the longevity and support of the platform technology” (2009: 38). For similar reasons, the library also reported issues with the preservation of legal deposit of video game magazines, which sometimes were bundled with physical DVD demo disks. Those could not be preserved without access to legacy hardware, or via some circumvention technique (2009: 40). Challenges to preservation caused by DRM locks on legacy hardware devices and file formats was similarly identified by Walters (2013) who notes that in contrast to traditional archives:

／ **Those responsible for the preservation of e-books must maintain the long-term usability of content (through the migration of file formats, for instance), the authenticity of content (including text, images, and page formats), discoverability (the preservation of metadata within the e-book or its package), and accessibility (through the maintenance or emulation of e-book readers, interfaces, and other access mechanisms) (Walters, 2013: 200).**

The complexity involved in preservation of digital materials emerges as a significant source of frustration for institutions dealing with TPMs. As Klein and White (2022) discuss, digital preservation does not consist solely of making copies (a function itself inhibited by TPMs) but may involve other processes such as migrating an object from one file structure to another to avoid obsolescence or emulating a software environment used by original hardware to enable access to content otherwise inaccessible (2022: 198). Original rightsholders or DRM providers may no longer be in business, further complicating preservation efforts (Erickson and Rodriguez Perez, 2024).

A study conducted by LIBER/LACA in 2020 surveyed research professionals working in higher education institutions in Europe. Most responses related to accessing e-journals, but also identified TPMs in databases, newspaper archives, websites and video platforms. When asked to describe specific TPMs encountered, most specified that IP blocking, access restrictions or other limitations (such as CAPTCHA) had been used to stop text and data mining (TDM) practices. In some cases, to safeguard existing access to specific databases from breach of licence terms, institutions had to apply their own technical limitations. For example, a French higher education institution described having to “install technical brakes with our reverse proxy”, meaning that they internally prevented academic members of staff from using text and data-mining practices on a specific database, to avoid triggering a suspension of access by the provider. This was despite the fact that licence terms for the database did not explicitly prohibit undertaking TDM.

An important feature of the LIBER/LACA survey is that it sought information about uptake of legal or administrative processes to request removal of TPMs for use benefiting of an exception, one of the first studies to do so. Article 3 of the Copyright in the Digital Single Market (CDSM) Directive introduced an exception for text and data mining benefiting research institutions. As previously noted under Art. 6(4) InfoSoc Directive, Member States must “ensure that rightholders make available ... the means of benefiting from that exception or limitation”. National implementations differ in the measures to ensure that rightsholders make available protected works to beneficiaries of exceptions.

Among the respondents who made formal requests to a publisher or government body to request access, there was a wide variation in success rate and processing time. Response times varied between 24 hours and 2.5 months to resolve content blocking issues. The mean waiting time reported was 24 days. One fifth of respondents were only partially able to resolve the issue and 11% said it was never resolved. In 12.5% of cases, the issue was only resolved after agreeing to additional payment (LIBER/LACA, 2020).

In 2024 the European Commission (DG RTD) published a substantial report analysing barriers to the access and reuse of publicly funded research, including scientific publications and data. The policy aim of the study was to "Propose an EU copyright and data legislative and regulatory framework fit for research" (2024: 3). The study analysed various impacts of copyright law on researchers and institutions using methods including surveys, interviews and document analysis. The survey indicated that 59.6% of researchers encountered online access restrictions and that these were a major impediment to research. The study also found that the presence of TPMs in conjunction with contractual licences prevented researchers from being able to benefit from copyright exceptions and significantly impeded research and innovation (2024: 27). Article 6(4) of the InfoSoc Directive limits the ability to request removal of TPMs to those researchers having "legal access" to materials, which themselves may be covered by restrictive licences (2024: 150). The report identified legal uncertainty and complexity as overall barriers to both institutions and researchers when using material as well as when making available new data and research results. An important finding is that TPMs impact not only access to traditional copyright materials such as e-books and audiovisual content, but also research data and innovative activities. For example, by impeding access to training data and the ability to perform text-and-data mining, TPMs may inhibit innovation in machine learning and AI. Use of different TPM protocols and techniques by various providers in different territories leads to an unpredictable landscape for research and innovation. TPMs therefore inhibit the realisation of a European "single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology" (2024: 154).

2.2 ACCESSIBILITY, TEACHING AND LEARNING

The initial survey by Akester (2009) also identified frustrations arising from TPMs among members of the public with accessibility needs, individual researchers and users. Notably, access for visually impaired users was found to be inhibited by TPMs. While popular e-book readers on PC had the capability to provide audio versions of e-books via text-to-speech (TTS), the feature could be restricted via TPM by choice of the publisher. Akester found that large technology providers like Microsoft and Adobe that could provide TTS in their e-book reading systems sometimes turned the feature off on request from publishers, such as when rights had been sold in an audiobook version (2009: 41). University lecturers, particularly in film and media studies, noted frustrations when dealing with TPM-protected materials in the classroom. Some relied on their own technical expertise to circumvent restrictions, while others relied on University IT support where available. Respondents reported using their own personal media collections for teaching, although noting that their institutions should provide that resource as part of their educational mission. A survey of university students also revealed that many encountered TPM restrictions in the course of their learning (2009: 58). A significant number reported that they relied on their own expertise or on third-party tools downloaded from the internet to circumvent TPMs on media such as DVDs.

A recent study by Roncevic (2020) found that the presence of digital locks in educational materials continues to pose challenges for teaching and learning in higher education. She argues that while internet technologies have facilitated access to knowledge broadly across society, the presence of TPMs may be one reason why libraries have lagged in offering digital models for search and discovery of information, since TPMs make e-books less appealing for both libraries and users (2020: 25). Impediments on the user side include the ability to benefit from copyright exceptions or make transformative uses of materials, which are important features for students and researchers. In a systematic review of barriers to e-book adoption, Girard (2014) similarly identified that barriers to print, annotate, copy and paste were among the most frequently reported impediments encountered by users. Furthermore, limited user options and cumbersome interfaces – often exacerbated by TPMs – reduce the utility of library-accessed digital materials. The disutility of TPM-enabled media for consumers has been identified and discussed widely in relation to arrange of different media types (Dorr et al., 2009; van Arnhem & Barnett, 2014; Erickson et al., 2017; Blummer et al., 2020; Volckmann, 2024). A survey by Roncevic (2024) found that 74 percent of college and university students believed there should be no restrictions on how e-books are used; 66 percent preferring to use e-books with no restrictions; and 37 percent reporting they would only use e-books with no restrictions when conducting research.

For libraries in the higher education context, the main problems identified by were a lack of local control, accompanied by external monitoring of usage by providers, introducing privacy concerns; second, the human resource cost of negotiating complex contracts; and third, impediments to archiving and preservation (Roncevic, 2020: 25). The author noted that some publishers and content providers like EBSCO, ProQuest, JSTOR, and Project MUSE had begun providing TPM-free titles as access options, but that public-facing libraries had an opposite experience, with more rather than fewer TPM restrictions placed on e-books (2020: 26)

Summary of previous research on TPMs in education, research and preservation

User Group	Issues reported	Main authors
Libraries, archives and research institutions	Lending: limits on number of users and simultaneous access	Akester, 2009; Walters, 2014; Roncevic, 2020
	Archiving and preservation – ability to make copies	Akester, 2009; Roncevic, 2020; Klein & Whyte, 2022
	Archiving and preservation – cost and complexity of maintaining access to legacy media	Akester, 2009; Walters, 2013
	User privacy and data protection concerns	Roncevic, 2020
	Slow, burdensome and ambiguous processes to request removal of TPMs	LIBER/LACA, 2020; European Commission, 2024
	Lack of legal clarity about relationship between TPMs and copyright exceptions	Renda et al., 2015; European Commission, 2024;
Individual researchers, students and library patrons	Accessibility (e.g. for visually impaired)	Akester, 2009;
	Ability to annotate, copy extracts and modify	Girard, 2014; Roncevic, 2020;
	Impediments to teaching and learning, e.g. ability to show clips or extracts	Akester, 2009; European Commission, 2024
	Impediments to innovation such as machine learning, AI and TDM	LIBER/LACA, 2020
	Disutility of materials compared to DRM-free (e.g. due to interface and other limitations)	Girard, 2014; Van Arnhem & Barnett, 2014; Roncevic, 2024;

Table 1: Summary of previous research on TPMs in education, research and preservation

3. RESEARCH METHOD AND SURVEY DESIGN

A survey approach was chosen for this study, to maximise coverage of both individual and institutional experiences of TPMs. To generate a wide range of responses, and in line with previous research in this domain, we opted to survey different stakeholder groups using broadly similar questions to enable comparison. Separate survey instruments were developed for both individual researchers and institutions using the Qualtrics online survey platform, with questions generated from the gaps identified in previous research efforts and aiming to provide a richer narrative of the challenges associated with TPMs.

Individual researchers were provided the survey link via the Knowledge Rights 21 mailing list and website, as well as the mailing list and website of CREATE at the University of Glasgow where the authors of the study were located. The invitation to complete the survey was further circulated via social media (Twitter, LinkedIn). Using the mailing list subscribers and social media followers of both organisations (KR21 and CREATE), we estimate that 1830 individuals received a link to the survey, yielding a response rate of 134 valid responses or approximately 7.6%. We received individual responses from 17 countries, with the highest number of responses coming from Germany, followed by the UK, Austria, Greece, Netherlands and Finland. More details on the demographics of individual respondents are provided in section 5 below. Among the individual respondents, 46% reported being affiliated with a research institution such as a university or library (students, lecturers/professors, research professionals). 54% of respondents were unaffiliated with a research institution (entrepreneurs, independent scholars, employees of a business or non-profit).

To target libraries and archives, we circulated our survey to member institutions of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) using their internal mailing list. We further boosted our sample using lists of UK and European national and higher education institutions obtained during previous research by the authors (Deazley and Stobo, 2013). We further expended our sample using desk research using sources such as the UK Government website and the Times Higher Education website. We used follow-up web search to identify the name, role title, and contact details of institution directors, plus a named member of staff with responsibility for copyright, research data management, or similar. Finally, a generic enquiries e-mail address was added as a contact of last resort. A similar process was undertaken using research assistants with native language fluency to locate names of prospective respondents in EU Member States. Google translate was used when searching the websites of European institutions for which we did not have access to a native speaker. This desk research produced contact names at 148 UK institutions and 60 European institutions, with a mixture of national libraries and university libraries identified in each of the 27 EU Member States.

Our preference was to address initial e-mail invitations to the library director or responsible staff member by name, to increase the chances of a response; having alternative e-mails was helpful in cases where e-mails were returned undelivered. Word and PDF copies of the survey instrument were included to help respondents prepare their answers in advance, particularly in larger institutions where coordination was required between departments.

Initial e-mail contact was made with each institution in the week commencing 5 February 2024, with a follow-up e-mail after 2 weeks and a final reminder before the survey closed on 6 March 2024. Both the institutional and individual user surveys were widely publicised and shared via Knowledge Rights 21 and CREATE official channels on 6 February 2024, including mailing lists and social media. From a sample of 208 institutions contacted, we received 92 valid responses, representing a response rate of 44%. Responses were received from 17 different countries, with the highest number of responses coming from the UK, Germany, Netherlands, Hungary and Finland. Among the respondents, 64.8% were very large institutions with more than 100 FTE staff, 14.7% were medium sized (21–99 FTE staff) and 20.5% were small (under 20 FTE employees). More detail on the institutional sample is provided in section 4 below.

One specific aim of the institutional survey was to gather key details about the institutions themselves, e.g. using the number of full time equivalent (FTE) staff employed as a measure of their overall size. For both individual and institutional groups, Likert-style questions were used to gauge knowledge of, and confidence with, copyright law. A mix of closed and open questions were used to gather more information about experiences of working with TPMs. In addition to the types of TPMs encountered and their impact, we were particularly interested in how publishers responded to requests to “unlock” content, and whether national mechanisms for removing TPMs are effective. Care had to be taken with the anonymity of participating institutions, given the sensitive nature of some of the questions asked: we wanted to find out if any institutions had attempted to circumvent TPMs, and if so, how they had approached this task. Due to sensitivity of these questions, responses are pseudonymised and only reported at the country level in our reported results. We use a coding system to pseudonymise the results, for example (DE RL 50) would indicate a research library from Germany corresponding to response #50 in our dataset. The code RL is used for university research libraries, while SC refers to special collections libraries and PL refers to public lending libraries. For individuals we pseudonymise responses by country, so (NO 102) would represent an individual respondent from Norway, response #102 in our dataset.

An additional purpose of the individual user survey was to explore the different scenarios in which an ordinary individual might encounter TPMs, e.g. when engaged in personal research or study, engaged in personal recreation, in the course of their paid employment, as a business owner, or as a volunteer community member. The bulk of survey questions were identical to those asked of institutions: we asked about the types of content locks they have encountered, how they react to them, and their experiences of seeking removal via formal requests to publishers and rightsholders. Copies of the survey instruments are provided in Appendix 1.

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4. FINDINGS: SURVEY OF INSTITUTIONS

This section presents the findings from our survey of institutions, which included national archives, national libraries, university research libraries and other institutions supporting research such as special collections libraries. After sifting out incomplete responses, there were 92 valid institutional responses to the survey. Responding institutions ranged in type as well as size (see Figure 1). The majority of responses were from university research libraries (78%), while the remainder came from national libraries or archives (6.6%), public lending libraries (5.6%), special collections libraries (5.5%), and other types (4.4%), consisting of an online archive, a museum, a school library and a subject-specialist university library. Responding institutions varied by size, from very small institutions with 1–5 FTE staff (9%), small institutions with 6–20 FTE staff (11.5%), medium institutions with 21–50 FTE staff (5.5%) large institutions with 50–99 FTE members of staff (9%) and very large institutions of 100+ FTE staff (65%). The countries of responding institutions were as follows: UK (35.9%), Germany (15.2%), Netherlands (8.7%), Hungary (8.7%), Finland (8.7%), Greece (4.3%), all other Europe (12%), country not provided (6.5%).

Figure 1: Size and type of responding institutions

Based on our review of existing literature, it is clear that TPMs can pose impediments to library-centric functions such as lending, interlibrary loan, on-site access, preservation and public engagement as well as support for research carried out by patrons. Responding institutions were first asked about the nature of TPMs encountered on works in their collections.

Our questionnaire was designed to capture a range of digital content locks, which included not only traditional technological protection measures, but other controls that might be categorised as Digital Rights Management (DRM) approaches. DRM can include both access controls (limiting what users can do with a work, such as print or download) as well as copy controls, which limit reproduction. Our survey took a broad approach to TPMs and digital access controls, and we included online authentication² and other access restrictions based on geographical location (geo-blocking), to ascertain the extent of those limitations on access experienced by institutions across a range of media types.

As expected, online authentication was the most common form of limitation on access, followed by limits on downloading and other forms of restriction such as printing and copying. Several institutions noted server authentication blocks to viewing content online, even when they had legal access to the material (DE MU respondent 9). In another case, online access was restricted to the IP range of the accessing institution only, in contradiction to the institution’s understanding of the licence terms, causing difficulties for remote users (FI NL Respondent 85). More than one third (38%) of institutions reported limits on interoperability, meaning the ability to transfer content from one device format to another, or to enable two devices or systems to interface with one another. A smaller but significant number of respondents (18%) reported limits on the ability to repair or reverse-engineer, suggesting that some libraries and archives were dealing with hardware locks in the course of carrying out their work. TPMs applied to computer hardware may inhibit preservation of digital media such as video games as well as digital content requiring tablets, kiosks, projectors, e-readers or smart TV devices.³ Limits to access based on geographic location (geo-blocking) were reported by 35% of institutions. Two institutions expressly detailed that they encountered TPMs when attempting text and data mining (DE SL Respondent 61; UK RL Respondent 50). One institution flagged up time-based limits on access, for example when borrowing and lending e-book materials (NL RL Respondent 79).

Figure 2: Types of TPMs encountered

² Not all definitions of TPMs include online access restrictions, however the DG RTD study in 2024 considered the impact of paywalls on accessibility of publicly funded research (European Commission, 2024). Similarly, Rosborough (2024) includes online content controls such as geo-blocking among current technological protection measures. Online authentication can work as a form of access control (for example technological measures may limit the number of articles accessed or downloaded depending on licence terms).

³ See Report 3 by Erickson, K. and Rodriguez Perez F. (2024) Technological Protection Measures and Digital Preservation: Evidence from Video Games. Knowledge Rights 21 Report DOI - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14165368>

Overall, the responses highlight that DRM restrictions are widely encountered by institutions, relating to a range of different actions that libraries and archives might be expected to legally undertake (such as providing access to users or allowing them to download and print excerpts of material).

Responding institutions reported encountering TPMs across a broad range of media types (Figure 3). The media types impacted by TPMs and digital locks reflect the overall transition towards digital and web-based content, while physical media TPMs continue to remain relevant in the institutional context. It should be noted that these results are influenced by the type of institutions that responded to our survey, which skewed heavily towards university research libraries. Among survey respondents, scholarly publishing represented the media type where TPMs were most frequently encountered, with 79% of institutions reporting TPMs on e-books and 67% on e-journals. Datasets were also frequently impacted, with TPMs on databases reported by 64% of institutions. While this is intuitive, given the widespread adoption of internet-accessible databases and electronic materials, the picture is different from what was encountered as recently as a decade ago, when e-books were emerging but physical media playback devices were still commonly used (for example, compare with Akester, 2009). Our results highlight the growing importance of online access restrictions and licensing in the research and education sector and the complex interrelationship between TPMs and licence terms. In many cases our respondents reported that TPMs frustrate or prevent uses of online material that would otherwise be allowed under the licence terms, for example preventing certain IP ranges from accessing online materials, or artificially throttling or suspending access after automated detection of repeat downloads from the same IP address.

Within audiovisual content we see a similar pattern, with streaming services for film and video (26% of institutions) and digital files (18%) now raising issues related to digital locks. Physical discs such as CDs and DVDs were still identified as a source of TPM restrictions in both music (29%) and film/video content (20%), indicating that libraries are still holding and making available media stored on legacy physical media formats. In other media types, it is notable that 21% of institutions reported encountering TPMs when dealing with images, including when accessing their own digitised materials (18%). Websites (22%), software (22%) and video games (10%) were also indicated by some institutions as a source of TPM restrictions. It is likely that the low proportion reporting encounters with TPMs in software and video games relates to the nature of the institutions surveyed: University research libraries likely do not deal with video games as much as specialist organisations. Nevertheless, digital materials appear to be on the rise as institutions of all types adopt new technologies. Overall, we observe that TPMs span a range of media types as well as formats, including online, streaming, locally stored digital files, legacy media collections and hardware devices.

Figure 3: TPMs encountered by media type (% of institutions that encountered)

One aim of the survey was to ascertain where the presence of TPMs raised challenges for institutions in carrying out their public mission. We queried respondents about difficulties encountered when carrying out the main traditional roles of lending, research, learning and teaching, public engagement, and preservation (as identified in the previous literature, see in particular Girard, 2014; Roncevic, 2020; Klein & Whyte, 2022). We also included uses of materials covered by relevant copyright exceptions, such as text and data mining, providing for accessibility, and format shifting (see Favale, 2011). The areas in which TPM restrictions were most frequently identified were research, lending, learning and teaching. This is perhaps intuitive as these are main functions of research libraries. Research activities involve not only access, but often the ability to download, manipulate, print and share materials – actions that can be restricted by TPMs. Text and data mining was also frequently impeded by TPMs as reported by many respondents, indicating the increasing prevalence of this research method and the potential hindrance from TPMs. Somewhat counterintuitively, on-site access for visitors was also reported to be impeded by TPMs by 33% of institutions. This may be explained by the move towards providing online access of digitised materials, where TPMs can be encountered even when access is attempted through institutional terminals. Approximately 20% of institutions reported that TPMs inhibited accessibility, format shifting and preservation, uses ordinarily covered by copyright exceptions. Exhibitions, while a function of some public-facing institutions, were not reported as frequently impeded, likely because they involve physical, static displays of material rather than online access.

Figure 4: Functions of responding institutions impeded by TPMs.

We surveyed respondents about the actions they might take in response to encountering TPMs (Figure 5). Nearly half (48%) of institutions indicated that they would avoid acquiring or using material that was protected by TPMs, indicating that these measures factor into institutional decisions about collections, including purchasing. A similar number of responding institutions (47%) would steer users towards other options (such as other institutions or access points) if TPMs inhibited the desired use, and 43% of respondents indicated that they would directly search for an alternative version of the material that did not contain TPMs, indicating that institutions may have multiple means of access available to them and that substitution may be possible in some cases. One university library noted that they would avoid purchasing DRM-protected material because TPMs on electronic materials made them unappealing from a user perspective:

Publishers' attempts to ensure the security of ebook services frequently result in a deterioration of user-experience and there is a lack of consistency on pricing or redress for changes in licensing terms within licence periods. (UK RL 74)

Both the reported aversion to acquiring material covered by TPMs, and the potential for alternative sources to supply institutional needs should give pause to publishers when applying aggressive TPMs to research materials, because their presence may reduce demand from institutional users in the long run. Furthermore, 30% of institutions indicated that when TPMs were present, they would avoid certain uses of the material not permitted by the TPMs. For example, one respondent indicated that when they encountered TPMs in digital collections, they let their acquisition team know of the issue to avoid renewal or purchase in future (AU RL Respondent 11). One Finnish special collections library indicated that they preferred to purchase books and technical standards documents in printed format only, because of the presence of TPMs on digital files (FI SC Respondent 81). While controlling access may be desirable from the perspective of a rightsholder seeking to limit use of copyright-protected material in specific ways, it suggests that some institutional users are not obtaining the full benefit of materials they have paid for, lowering the overall quality of that content in the

institutional context and possibly leading to future changes in purchasing behaviour (as noted by Roncevic, 2020, and others). In other words, over-use of TPMs may limit the quality and the market for materials from an institutional perspective, exacerbated by the availability of alternative sources where those exist. The lower quality of research materials available also undermines scientific research and innovation, with wider economic consequences for European competitiveness (EU Commission, 2024). One research library described the follow-on effect of TPMs on the experience of their users:

／ **TPMs are an inconvenience that restrict access across a range of items. This impacts the user experience which means that we cannot provide the best service that we could. We have limited staff and resources to be able to circumvent or challenge TPMs so we tend to accept them as they are, but that doesn't mean that we are happy about this. (UK RL Respondent 37)**

Legal uncertainty and lack of resources limited the actions that institutions could take in dealing with TPMs. Only a small number of responding institutions reported willingness to circumvent TPMs. Among our respondents, only 10% of institutions reported that they had searched for a method of circumventing a TPM, and only 4% reported actually applying a circumvention technique to access materials. This is probably due to legal uncertainty about the ability of privileged beneficiaries to apply circumvention to TPMs, and aversion to risk on the part of institutions. Library professionals may also lack the technical skills and resources to engage in circumvention. The behaviour of individual researchers (discussed in Section 5 below) indicates that perception of legal risk is more significant for institutions, since individuals report more willingness to circumvent TPMs, although both groups indicated legal uncertainty as a factor influencing their actions. A prominent theme that emerged from the responses was that institutions had limited human and technical resources to assess legal options or to engage with publishers to request removal, and this is borne out in the low rate of interaction with rightsholders or government administrative processes (see Figure 7).

Figure 5: Actions undertaken by institutions after encountering TPMs.

We further asked institutions about the approaches they might consider taking to either request removal of TPMs or to circumvent them. It is important to note that 45% of institutions surveyed declined to answer this question. As previously shown in Figure 5, only a small minority of respondents (10%) reported having searched for or applied TPM circumvention techniques in the past, suggesting risk-aversion. In terms of what they would consider when faced with a TPM that they wished to circumvent, 41% of institutions indicated that they would prefer to negotiate with rightsholders for removal before seeking other methods (see Figure 6). If they did undertake circumvention, 22% of institutions said that they would use their own in-house expertise to do so, and a similar number of 20% would use in-house expertise augmented by internet search. It is notable that only 18% said they would consider using a legal government process to request removal, suggesting limited awareness and uptake of these processes in jurisdictions where they are available.⁴ A minority of respondents (10%) reported willingness to apply third-party tools to enable circumvention, with qualitative evidence suggesting that this was the least desirable option due to perceived technological and reputational risk. One library elaborated that they “would be wary about using any third-party software or tool for this purpose” (UK RL 74). Another university library stated that they would actively dissuade students from attempting to circumvent TPM in ways that could breach their licence agreements with publishers (UK RL 76). A library from Denmark added that “this question implies illegal action, which we would not do” (DK RL 33).

In general, respondents reported overall low willingness to apply circumvention techniques to materials, but there were some specific instances where they did. One library reported that for fulfilment of inter-library loan requests, if an article could not be downloaded as a PDF, they would copy the full text content from the website into a word document and save that as PDF to be shared with the user. They went on to indicate that “there may be other similar scenarios where we are confident in our legal permission to circumvent TPM and would do so via an in-house method” (UK RL 74). One library that held collections of physical media noted that they had occasionally digitised DVDs, “but this was carried out by another department within the institution and [the respondent] did not know personally of any circumvention.” (IR NL 92).

Figure 6: Approaches considered when seeking to circumvent TPMs

⁴ Jurisdictions in Europe with formally administered complaint processes or mediating boards include the UK, Switzerland, Italy, Hungary, Greece, France, Finland, Estonia and Denmark. For further details, see the doctrinal analysis Report 1 by Rosborough (2024).

The copyright law of most European states places a formal obligation on rightsholders to make available the means of benefiting from specific copyright exceptions upon request from users seeking to access works protected by TPMs. The nature of the process to make such a request differs by territory, but the European countries that explicitly provide such a requirement in national law include: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Romania, Slovenia and Spain. For a full summary of national approaches to the obligations placed on rightsholders, see Report 1 by Rosborough (2024). Certain territories specify that rightsholders must additionally process requests within a reasonable period of time. For example, Slovenia and Bulgaria have both introduced provisions requiring rightsholders to respond within 72 hours of receiving a request.⁵ Ireland stipulates that rightsholders must make available the means of benefiting from an exception “within 30 days” of receipt of a request, and Estonia requires that rightsholders respond “within a reasonable period of time”.

Within our sample, 38% of institutions reported making a request to a rightsholder, and it was one of the more widely used responses to dealing with TPMs by institutions (See Figure 6). Within the total sample of surveyed institutions, 25% reported making a successful request to a rightsholder, while 4.3% were successful but only after agreeing to higher payment terms to enable access, and 8.7% made a request but were unsuccessful. The amount of time from request to decision varied widely, with 11.3% of all requests (representing 4.3% of institutions) settled in under 2 days, 25.7% of requests taking up to a week, 31.7% of requests taking up to a month and 20% of requests taking over 1 month to resolve.

Figure 7: Outcomes of institutional requests to rightsholders to remove TPMs

⁵ Under its implementation of the CDSM, Bulgaria included in Article 26(k)(1): When a user under Art. 26g has requested the holder of the right to provide him with access to the object of protection under the conditions and according to the order of Art. 25a, para. 2, the holder of the right is obliged to provide the necessary access within 72 hours of receipt of the request. See: <https://www.knowledgerights21.org/news-story/key-wins-on-knowledge-rights-21-priorities-in-bulgarias-implementation-of-the-digital-single-market-directive/>

These results corroborate the findings of the Liber/LACA (2020) survey, which found similarly slow response times from publishers. A further 11.3% of requests received no response from rightsholders. The fact that over 50% of requests took several weeks or longer to resolve, and a significant number of requests yielded no response from publishers, suggests that there are problems and inconsistencies with the responsiveness of TPM removal request mechanisms. When asked their preference for turnaround time on requests made to publishers, the majority indicated that 72 hours or less was an acceptable wait time for a response from publishers, suggesting that the current situation in practice is not meeting expectations (Table 2).

In certain jurisdictions, prospective users may also engage with a government or administrative process to request access to materials protected by TPMs if they are unable to obtain the necessary access from rightsholders.⁶ Among the surveyed institutions, only 6 institutions reported making a request to a government or administrative process. Of those, 4 institutions reported being successful in their requests. Those were in the jurisdictions of Greece, Finland, Germany and the United Kingdom. One other institution from Greece made an unsuccessful request that took several months to be processed, and one institution from the United Kingdom had made a request but was unsure about the ultimate outcome. One research library described their perception of the administrative TPM removal process as “open to interpretation, longwinded and costly” (UK RL Respondent 46). Previous results from Akester (2009) suggest that institutional resources may be an impediment to engaging with rightsholder or administrative processes. We tested whether size of institution correlated with reported engagement with a removal process, finding that medium and large institutions (>6 FTE employees) were 2-4 times more likely to engage with a rightsholder to request removal of TPMs compared with very small institutions (<5 FTE employees). This suggests that the resource costs of dealing with rightsholders regarding TPMs introduces equity imbalances, favouring larger and more resource-endowed institutions. There was no significant difference in likelihood to engage with a government administrative process, which was rare in either case.

In general, uptake of government administrative processes by responding institutions was very low. When asked about their expectations for processing time performance from a government administrative system, most respondents indicated that such a system should ideally provide a response in 5 working days or less (Table 2).

Acceptable processing time indicated by institutions for government and rightsholder TPM removal requests (% of responding institutions).						
Acceptable processing time:	24 hours	72 hours	5 working days	10 working days	1 month	3 months
Rightsholder	14%	42%	22%	14%	8%	0%
Government	4%	37%	27%	24%	4%	4%

Table 2: Acceptable processing time indicated by institutions for government and rightsholder TPM removal requests (% of responding institutions).

⁶. Jurisdictions in Europe with formally administered complaint processes or mediating boards include the UK, Switzerland, Italy, Hungary, Greece, France, Finland, Estonia and Denmark. For further details see Report 1 by Rosborough (2024).

Increasingly, library institutions provide access to materials and databases over the internet, enabled through a login authentication process. Publishers can control access and use of digital materials accessed this way, and they can also monitor usage for pricing purposes or to detect unauthorised access requests. In some cases, access may be temporarily or permanently suspended by an online provider due to detection of unusual activity on the part of the accessing institution. Online licence restrictions can often be more strict than what would normally be allowed under copyright law, interfering with exceptions. For example, the text and data mining exception enabled by Article 3 CDSM Directive should enable TDM activities by research institutions, even if rightsholders attempt to prevent this activity using contractual terms.⁷

We surveyed respondents about whether their access was ever suspended by a service provider and what the ultimate outcomes were. Among our respondents, 38% indicated that they had encountered suspension of their access by rightsholders/providers (Figure 8). The main triggers for suspension were high download activity (46% of reported suspensions), text and data mining by researchers affiliated with the institution (11%), use of bibliometric or other automated software tools (11%), large numbers of access requests (11%), and requests from unusual IP ranges (6%). In some cases, institutions reported that their access was suspended for no discernible reason (8.5% of suspensions). Text-and-data mining emerged as a major point of contention for a number of the institutions surveyed. One institution in the UK noted that "Primary source platforms (e.g. Gale and Proquest) put digital content locks on their platforms. This prevents TDM or data collection work at scale without additional fee for analytical tools." (UK RL 73). By contrast, a university research library in the Netherlands reported that, after having access suspended, they were able to assert that their TDM activities were legitimate, and had access reinstated (NL RL 12).

Among those that experienced an account suspension, 25.8% (9.8% of institutions) reported that they informed the provider that they believed their use was appropriate, and the issue was corrected. The remainder either did not notify the provider, or took some other action. In 8.4% of cases (3.2% of institutions), the institution decided to change to a different provider with more favourable access conditions. In the majority of suspensions (65.8% of cases, 25% of institutions) the institution changed their behaviour to comply with the access rules set by the provider in order to have access restored. Several responding institutions indicated that they contacted their users to make them aware of provider terms and conditions and ask them to comply with providers' rules, even when users were engaging in legitimate research activity. The fact that the majority of institutions, when faced with an account suspension, opted to change their behaviour, demonstrates a power imbalance, with publishers able to exert greater control over the usage of digital materials. One UK university library put in place their own stricter technical measures to avoid access being suspended, with a lower access threshold than those used by publishers to trigger access suspension (UK RL Respondent 87). They explained that the purpose was to ensure that the institution always complied and did not breach usage terms. This would obviously have the deleterious effect of limiting what researchers could do with electronic materials. Automated suspension rules and server-side TPMs were often opaque to institutions, causing them to be overly cautious for fear of triggering an automated suspension. In some cases, the cause of suspension was traced back to behaviour of specific users who were subsequently warned to abide by the licence terms (NL RL 79).

⁷ See: <https://blogs.ifa.org/lpa/2020/06/10/text-and-data-mining-articles-3-and-4-of-the-eu-dsm/>

Figure 8: Prevalence of online account suspension and outcome

It is notable that we asked whether institutions had sought a refund after encountering an account suspension, but none of the respondents reported doing so. This suggests a lack of bargaining power on the part of libraries and a power imbalance favouring providers of digital research materials. Compared to the results obtained from our survey of individual researchers, institutions did not report feeling able to request refunds or switch between different providers in the market if they were unhappy with licence conditions or TPMs imposed by a provider. One library described their experience when considering requesting a refund for unexpected DRM on purchased e-books as follows:

On one occasion we purchased an ebook collection and only discovered afterwards that there were DRM restrictions on some of the titles, limiting the number of simultaneous users. The requesting librarian still wanted the content regardless so we didn't push for a refund or to return the content, but voiced our concerns that the restrictions had not been stated in the product description. The publisher increased the user limit on those titles slightly in compensation for the misunderstanding. (UK RL Respondent 74)

The survey results point strongly towards the existence of a power imbalance between digital access providers and institutions, since the majority of respondents changed their behaviour to comply with terms of access rather than seek alternative remedies.

The fact that a significant number of reported suspensions arose from institutions carrying out normal and lawful work (text and data mining, bibliometric referencing and providing access to users) indicated that online access to materials is an area of significant concern. The inability of libraries and researchers to make full lawful use of digital materials suggests that in practical terms, overly restrictive licences and TPMs are hindering socially and economically valuable research and innovation and interfering with fundamental rights. While copyright law may technically enable institutions to request access from rightsholders and government bodies, in actual practice few are doing so, and many are reporting negative impacts from TPMs in everyday use. Institutions report limited resources, knowledge and training to deal with TPMs, along with an unnecessarily complex legal landscape characterised by different national approaches to requiring rightsholders to provide access, as well as absent or differing complaint/review processes by territory (see Rosborough, 2024).

We sought to gain insight about institutions' level of knowledge of copyright law in general and provisions concerning TPMs, specifically. We asked institutions to rate their agreement with statements in a series of 5-point Likert-style questions, with a range from "agree" (1) to "disagree" (5). The purpose of these questions was to gauge institutions' confidence in understanding and interpreting the law concerning TPMs, and their awareness of legal routes to request removal. Table 3 summarises the mean level of agreement with each question, cross-tabulated by size of institution. We find that, overall, institutions report a high level of confidence in their knowledge of copyright law, although the smallest institutions appear to be at a disadvantage compared to larger ones, suggesting equity concerns. This pattern of lower confidence among very small institutions continues across the different questions, indicating that legal knowledge is correlated with institutional resource capacity. Knowledge of the law concerning TPMs was lower across all institutions than their knowledge of copyright law in general. Institutions were not confident in their ability to circumvent TPMs, and this was strongest among very small institutions. Awareness of any legal administrative process to request removal of TPMs followed a similar pattern, with generally low awareness across the sample of institutions. Describing their institutional context, one university research library indicated that "pockets of expertise exist within the institution, but general awareness is somewhat lower" (UK RL 72). The pattern may also be different depending on the size and market power of the country in which institutions are located. One university library from Denmark indicated that because they deal with global publishers, the legal situation for them was more complex due to territoriality, and they were therefore unsure about which copyright provisions applied to which publishers and works (DK RL 83).

Statement:	We have knowledge about copyright law	We have knowledge about the law concerning TPMs	The law concerning exceptions is clear and understandable	We feel confident in our technical ability to circumvent TPMs	We are aware of legal administrative process to request removal
Size of institution (FTE staff)					
Micro (1-5)	2.0	3.6	3.0	5.0	5.0
Small (6-20)	1.5	2.0	2.6	3.2	3.4
Medium (21-50)	2.0	2.6	2.3	4.5	3.0
Large (51-100)	1.3	2.6	3.0	3.7	3.7
Very large (100+)	1.3	2.3	3.4	3.2	3.1

Table 3: Mean level of agreement by institution size (lower number indicates greater agreement)⁸

⁸ The Likert-style agreement statements were: (1) agree; (2) somewhat agree; (3) neither agree nor disagree; (4) somewhat disagree; (5) disagree.

4.1 SUMMARY: LIBRARIES AND TPMS

Our results indicate that many libraries, archives and research support institutions across Europe are having their work significantly impeded by TPMS. The institutions we surveyed identified impediments from TPMS across a range of library, education and research support functions. The most frequently reported impacts from TPMS were in the areas of research, lending, learning and teaching, text-and-data mining and providing access for on-site visitors. We also observed frequent suspensions of access, a lack of compensation for materials covered by TPMS and research activities being undermined with researchers being asked to modify their practices to avoid triggering automated TPMS. These impediments have major ramifications for fundamental rights, innovation and scientific advancement.

Institutions expressed uncertainty about the best course of action to undertake when faced with a TPM inhibiting an activity normally covered by an exception to copyright, such as making reproductions for the purpose of preservation, or undertaking non-commercial text and data mining. A limited number of institutions (38%) reported engaging with formal processes to request removal of TPMS, with mixed results. Response times are slow, often taking a month or longer. The majority of institutions had not engaged in such a formal process with rightsholders, and even fewer institutions (6 in total out of 92 surveyed) reported engaging with government administrative bodies to request removal of TPMS. Our survey shows that resources and legal knowledge to deal with TPMS are disproportionately skewed towards larger institutions, introducing equity concerns. For reasons of lack of resource capacity, lack of clarity in the law, and reputational risk, institutions are unable to benefit from the full use of materials protected by TPMS.

Institutions report that provider licence terms and TPMS are deeply intertwined. Disagreements occurred where there was different understanding between libraries and service providers about uses permitted by a licence. A digital provider may detect or automatically restrict access based on technological means, and these access restrictions may not correspond to institutions' understanding of licence terms. Sometimes respondents attempted to renegotiate licence terms with the provider, but frequently institutions changed their behaviour to avoid triggering automated access restrictions.

Box 1: Respondent voices

“An often overlooked effect of TPMs is that they are fundamentally incompatible with secure computer systems (particularly open source). If I have to install some questionable software to use content, I’m not going to.” (DE RL 192)

“Our preferred avenue would be alternate purchase formats that did not include TPMs; For streaming content in particular, there are no good ways to circumvent TPMs and we are not confident that a request process would be successful.” (RL 18)

“Updates to copyright legislation and electronic product licences would be more beneficial, for example coming improvements to the CLA licence to increase the proportion of a work that can be copied plus the ability to request content from the BL / CLA for use by a group i.e. a group of researchers.” (UK RL 46)

“We find that where TPMs are applied to ebooks purchased on an institutional licence, they not only prevent our Authorised Users using them to the full extent permitted by CIPA 1988, but also restrict our ability to share content with other institutional libraries under the terms of s.42A.” (UK RL 59)

“Publishers are aware of the law around TPM and in our experience actively use it to increase their revenue streams by selling alternative format versions of content that we already have legal access to.” (e.g. for TDM purposes)
(UK RL 74)

“We try to acquire content without content locks although in some cases there is no alternative. In these cases we will buy print content which is not helpful for distance learners or those with accessibility needs.” (UK RL 87)

“All our tax payer funded research should be openly accessible to the public.” (AT RL 113)

5. FINDINGS: INDIVIDUAL RESEARCHERS

This section presents the findings from our survey of individual researchers. After removal of incomplete or invalid surveys, there were 134 individual responses in the sample. Respondents were distributed nearly evenly between those affiliated with a university (such as research librarians, lecturers, and students) and non-affiliated researchers, such as those engaging in personal study, accessing materials for recreation, or engaging in entrepreneurial activities (See Figure 9). There were 17 countries represented in the survey responses, with 86.4% coming from within the European Union and 10.5% from non-EU European countries of the UK, Switzerland and Norway. In 3.1% of surveys returned the respondent did not provide their specific country of residence. The largest individual country represented in the sample was Germany (accounting for 45.3% of all responses), followed by the UK (accounting for 8.2% of all responses), followed by Austria (4.5%), Spain (4.5%), Greece (4.5%), Netherlands (3.7%), Finland (3%), Portugal (2.2%), Italy (2.2%), Sweden (2.2%), France (1.5%), Bulgaria (1.5%), Switzerland (1.5%), Norway (0.75%), Hungary (0.75%), Ireland (0.75%) and Poland (0.75%).

Figure 9: Sample characteristics of individual researcher survey

To enable comparison, we asked similarly structured questions to both individuals and institutions and retained the same answer choices where possible. Therefore, we asked individuals whether they encountered the same types of content locks as institutions, and we provided a free-text option to list any additional TPMs encountered. Overall, a greater number of individuals reported encountering TPMs or digital locks compared to institutions (Figure 10). Nearly all respondents (90%) reported that they had encountered online

authentication restrictions in the course of their research. Limits on downloading (78%) and limits on access (72%) were reported in the same order of importance as institutions, although more individuals reported encountering them. In contrast to the institutional sample, more individuals (66%) encountered limits based on geographic location. Similarly, limits on interoperability (e.g. the ability to access content across different devices) were more frequently reported among individuals (58%) than institutions (37%), suggesting different patterns of personal use. Limits on the ability to reverse-engineer and repair was also higher for individuals (32%), which is intuitive, given the wider range of uses that individuals may pursue involving different hardware devices. Individuals also reported a range of other limits they encountered. These included limits on playback of legacy media such as DVDs (UK 232), limits on website access metered behind requests to collect personal data (DE 156; DE 190), access restrictions when attempting to lawfully access material from behind a proxy or VPN service used for privacy reasons (DE 217), and limits on the ability to view content in accessible formats (AT 104). One respondent suggested that websites that display only one page of a document at a time function as a kind of digital lock, because that behaviour limits the ability to perform automated tasks such as text and data mining (DE 153).

Figure 10: Digital content locks and TPMs encountered by individual researchers

Compared with the institutions surveyed, individual researchers encountered TPMs across a broader range of media types (Figure 11). Scholarly publishing remained the most reported media type impacted by TPMs for individuals, but it made up a smaller proportion of the overall “basket” of media impacted by TPMs. Within the scholarly publishing category, e-books (91%) and e-journals (85%) were the most frequently reported. More individuals reported content restrictions in audio-visual streaming services than institutions, with 62% of individuals reporting difficulty accessing video streaming content and 47% music streaming content. In general, TPMs on audio-visual content in all formats (files, discs, and streaming) were more frequently identified by individual researchers. TPMs on software (55%) and hardware (45%) were also more frequently identified by individual researchers, along with video games (35%). A considerable number of individuals (28%) also reported encountering content locks on digital images. These results suggest that individuals are seeking to access

content across a wider range of interactive media and devices that may not be as common in traditional library holdings but nevertheless present challenges to researchers and users. It is also notable that only 3% of individuals surveyed reported TPMs on websites, while this figure was significantly higher for institutions, suggesting that the web services more commonly accessed through libraries make greater or more apparent use of content locks.

Figure 11: TPMs encountered by media type (% of individuals that encountered)

In terms of specific challenges raised by TPMs and digital content locks, responses were highly varied depending on the individual context of the user and the type of research undertaken. For university-affiliated researchers, a common issue was engaging in TDM, often when using materials that were lawfully accessed via their institution. One UK research librarian reported that they were often called upon to support researchers “using the content we have paid for or that we have the right to data-mine from publishers, but access to this content can be a minefield!”. (UK respondent 139)

National context was also an important factor in researcher experiences with TPMs. One respondent from Norway reported that access limitations based on geographic location was a significant hindrance:

“ I work in film studies but live in a small country where many distributors don’t even bother releasing certain films. However, for some reason, they do geo-block access to them on Amazon, Google Play, iTunes, etc. So in effect most films that are released in Europe are permanently unavailable for me to see – or to teach. To be clear, I would pay for content – but in most cases, that is not an option, so of course I (like most of the academic film and media studies community) have to resort to alternative means to get hold of films for research and teaching. (NO respondent 136)

Non-affiliated researchers encountered frequent problems accessing and using materials. Published research was often located behind a paywall, and many researchers lamented that publicly funded research and other public domain information was frequently locked behind access restrictions (AT 111). One respondent noted frustration when trying to access DIN/EN/ISO standards “that are mandated by the law to implement”, and should therefore be freely available (DE 108). Another German entrepreneur noted that speed of access was a significant deterrent against engaging with TPM-protected content:

／ **In my line of work I usually need access to a document quickly, so even a 24-hour wait is too slow. I would have to either circumvent the protection or (most of the time) just search for other sources. (DE 138)**

Finally, both university-affiliated and non-affiliated researchers sometimes performed research using materials outside of the traditional library environment, such as content from social media, web scraped data, music and video content from their own media collections, all of which were potentially impeded by TPMs or other digital locks.

Figure 12: Responses to encountering TPMs by individual researchers

We surveyed individual respondents about the actions they might take in response to encountering TPMs (Figure 12). Individuals were generally more willing to take action in response to TPMs and took a wider variety of approaches compared to institutions. Nearly 80% of individual respondents indicated that they had avoided purchasing or using material that was restricted by a TPM, and 69% reported that they had searched for a substitute product without TPM protection. A similar 68% of respondents indicated that they had sought alternative access to the same product but without protection, through a different platform or provider. The reasons for seeking out alternative versions of material, even from unlawful sources, was not always related to cost. Respondents cited increased performance and utility from services without TPMs:

／ **Many legal sources for accessing articles, for which my institution already has subscriptions, are slower and less convenient than illegal places [and volunteer repositories], which almost always “just work”, and I don’t need to mess around with VPN, Authenticators, creating login accounts, etc. (UK respondent 123)**

By necessity, access to TPM-protected web-accessible materials requires authentication by the user and compliance with any licence terms. These steps can add frustration, particularly if the user is working from an unknown IP range or wishes to perform actions with the material such as lawful text and data mining that may trigger an account suspension. For those unwilling or unable to circumvent TPMs, 34.5% noted that they were forced to avoid certain uses of the material that they otherwise would have been able to enjoy. The ability to modify and format-shift were cited as one source of increased utility from avoiding TPM-protected materials:

I am familiar with using third party software to remove TPM from ebooks, and use it frequently to back up ebooks I have purchased and to be able to edit/change fonts, size, layout etc. for my own readability, beyond options available via Kindle etc. (UK 186)

Not all individual researchers reported willingness to circumvent TPMs, but a much higher proportion were willing to do so compared to the institutional sample. 58% of individuals indicated that they had searched for a means of circumventing TPMs, and 50% said they had applied a circumvention technique to obtain access. There was general awareness of legal prohibitions on circumvention of TPMs among the respondents, and a number of those surveyed offered explanations for their unwillingness to apply circumvention to remain in compliance with the law. In response to the survey question on whether they were willing to apply circumvention, one respondent from France noted, "isn't that illegal?" (FR 213) while another in Germany responded, "I don't circumvent TPM locks" (DE 178). One respondent from Portugal indicated their reliance on a 2017 exception to copyright which grants end users a right to circumvent TPMs on certain works (PT 226). For users in jurisdictions where there was no such relevant exemption, but where they were still willing to personally circumvent TPMs, some justified their actions in reference to activities that would normally be possible with physical media (DE 190), while others emphasised the incompatibility of TPMs with other concerns such as privacy and cybersecurity (DE 189). Some indicated that the high cost of TPM-protected academic materials was a deterrent to seeking lawful access (DE 182; DE 148). Others argued that publicly-funded research outputs should be freely available (AT 111).

Figure 13: Approaches considered when seeking to circumvent TPMs

For those respondents who were willing to undertake circumvention on their own, either because they believed they benefited from an exemption or because they believed their actions were justified, their feedback highlights a wide availability of alternative means of access. A significant number of respondents indicated that they would consider bypassing TPMs using their own technical expertise (60%) or augmented by internet search (72%). Respondents noted that a wide variety of alternative scientific repositories were available to access e-books and e-journals, as well as third-party tools such as peer-to-peer file sharing services and other format-shifting or ripping services for capturing streams and other content. Respondents also commonly used author-upload repositories such as SSRN, ResearchGate and Academia.edu to access materials when they were unavailable from a publisher.

For those seeking removal of TPMs, another alternative was to make a request directly to a rightsholder (29%) or to make a formal request via an administrative process in jurisdictions where that was possible (24%). Many individual researchers interpreted “request to a publisher or rightsholder” differently from the institutional group, noting their preferred solution was to reach out to academic authors directly to request pre-prints of work that was otherwise inaccessible. Those direct approaches to authors also resulted in a higher reported success rate.

Figure 14: Outcomes of individual requests to rightsholders to remove TPMs

Figure 14 summarises the outcomes for the 29% of individual respondents who reported making a request to a publisher or rightsholder to request removal of TPMs. The proportion of respondents who made such a request is slightly lower than for the institutional sample, perhaps indicating lower awareness of legal routes to access among individual researchers. In 67% of cases, representing 19.5% of all respondents, individuals reported that their request for access was successful. In 33% of cases (9.5% of all respondents) requests to rightsholders were unsuccessful, either receiving a negative response or no response at all from rightsholders. A small number of cases were resolved after additional payment by the individual making the

request. The overall time to receive a response was improved for individuals compared to institutions, but this may reflect the propensity for some users to request individual pre-prints directly from authors. These were normally resolved swiftly, with 29% of requests resolved in under 2 days, and another 29% of requests resolved in under one week. In 23% of cases, a response took 2 weeks or longer, and in 18% of cases there was no response from a publisher/rightsholder. It took longer to receive a negative response than a positive one, on average.

While 24% of individual researchers indicated that they would consider making a request to a government or other administrative process to request removal of TPMs, only 11 individuals (8% of respondents) provided details about an attempt at doing so. Compared to rightsholder requests, the purpose of making requests to a formal administrative process was usually to gain prolonged access to a wider number of works, such as those in a database or media collection. Just under half (45%) of administrative requests by individuals were reported as being successful, while 55% of cases were unsuccessful or still awaiting a response at the time of completing the survey. The majority (64%) of these requests had taken 2 weeks or longer, and some had not been resolved after several months. Overall, the experience of users engaging in legal requests was slow and cumbersome and the majority of individuals surveyed did not engage with rightsholders or government administrative processes.

When asked what they thought an acceptable response time would be from both rightsholders and government administrative processes, the majority of respondents considered 72 hours or less to be an acceptable processing time (Table 4). Individual respondents expected publishers to be able to respond rapidly, and individuals expected an even more rapid response than institutions did (compare with Table 2). This could reflect the different uses of these mechanisms by individuals, who tended to seek removal of TPMs from single items for specific lawful purposes, rather than more complex requests involving collections and databases.

Acceptable processing time indicated by institutions for government and rightsholder TPM removal requests (% of responding institutions).						
Acceptable processing time:	24 hours	72 hours	5 working days	10 working days	1 month	3 months
Rightsholder	33.5%	27%	18.5%	17.5%	2.5%	1%
Government	21%	35.5%	19%	13%	9.5%	2%

Table 4: Acceptable processing times for rightsholder and government TPM removal requests (% of individuals indicating that preference).

As with the institutions we surveyed, research by individuals increasingly involves online access to materials, mediated by third-party providers and platforms. We queried individuals about whether their access had ever been suspended by a provider and what the outcome of that suspension was. Among our respondents, 24.4% indicated that they had faced suspension of access due to their research activity (Figure 15). The main causes of suspension were large quantities of access requests (23.5% of reported suspensions), user browser configuration such as privacy or ad-blocking (20.5%), high download activity (14.7%), geolocation (14.7%), text-and-data mining (5.8%) and printing (2.9%).

Users reported frequent frustration as a result of geographic restrictions, usually when they were accessing materials remotely from their university institution, or when they were using a VPN or other privacy or cybersecurity measure. Users, as opposed to institutions, access the Internet from a wider variety of systems and IP ranges, and this appears to result in more frequent access restrictions. One user from Germany reported that, "for technical (not privacy) reasons my internet traffic originates from a datacentre, however popular hosting providers (e.g. Hetzner, OVH, etc.) are often blocked from viewing content due to a generalised assumption that these are crawlers" (DE 190). Use of privacy tools such as adblockers or settings to increase browser privacy, such as restricting JavaScript or cookies, were also reported as causes of access suspension (IT 124; DE 164). It should be noted that individual users also undertook text-and-data mining on a wide range of online materials, not limited to academic journals or databases. One user reported that their access to Twitter was throttled by the platform when attempting to perform web scraping for social science research (UK 232).

Among those respondents that experienced an account suspension, 2.8% reported that they contacted the provider about the issue, and that the provider took steps to correct the problem. Most individual researchers did not attempt to directly contact the provider. More frequently, the user changed their behaviour to comply with the platform rules (26.2% of cases). This may reflect reticence by individuals to complain or attempt to negotiate with providers, perceiving they have low bargaining power. However, individuals reported more willingness to move to competing services, compared to institutions. In 35.2% of cases, individual researchers reported switching to a different provider as a result of an access suspension. In another 35.2% of cases the problem was resolved on its own without a response from the provider. These cases of automatic resolution may be explained by the widespread use of temporary lock-outs, for example used to mitigate traffic spikes or server overload from a large number of simultaneous access requests. In one case, an individual user involved their academic institution to negotiate with the provider on their behalf, but the result was that the researcher had to change their crawling behaviour to regain access to the provider's website (SE 223). Overall, the results suggest that providers are not very attentive to the issues faced by individual researchers accessing online materials. While individuals appear to have somewhat more ability than institutions to switch to competing providers or repositories if they do not have a good experience with a publisher, overall individual researchers reported negative experiences related to digital locks when accessing research materials online from publishers.

Figure 15: Prevalence of online account suspension and outcome

We asked individual researchers to rate their agreement with a series of Likert-style questions to gauge their overall knowledge of copyright law and TPMs, and their knowledge of legal administrative processes to request removal of TPMs. We provided similar statements to both individual and institutional respondents to facilitate comparison (compare with Table 3 above). The scale ranged from (1) “agree” to (5) “disagree” with (3) indicating “neither agree nor disagree”. Table 5 presents the mean level of agreement with each statement by individuals, cross-tabulated by affiliation of the researcher. University-affiliated researchers include all those who indicated their role as a student in a higher education institution as well as lecturers and professional staff. Non-affiliated researchers were those engaged in personal research or study, and those working in roles outside of universities, which included non-profit and commercial settings. Overall, we found that individual researchers of all types expressed good knowledge of copyright law, although this lowered when it came to knowledge of anti-circumvention provisions and specific exceptions to copyright. Compared to all but the smallest institutions, individuals were generally less aware of legal administrative processes to request removal of TPMs. University-affiliated researchers reported lower awareness of legal administrative processes, perhaps because they relied on their institutions to make requests on their behalf. University-affiliated researchers were slightly more confident in their knowledge about copyright law and the law concerning TPMs. On average, both groups of researchers disagreed that the law concerning exceptions was clear and understandable.

Statement:	I have knowledge about copyright law	I have knowledge about the law concerning TPMs	The law concerning exceptions is clear and understandable	I feel confident in my technical ability to circumvent TPMs	I am aware of legal administrative process to request removal
Type of Researcher					
Non-affiliated	1.77	2.69	3.84	3.02	3.84
University affiliated	1.66	2.31	3.92	2.83	4.24

Table 5: Mean level of agreement by researcher affiliation (lower number indicates greater agreement)⁹

Finally, we report findings for both individuals and institutions in response to the last set of Likert-style questions, which evaluated whether TPMs impacted their research activity and whether legal mechanisms to request removal of TPMs would help their work (Table 6). On average, both groups reported that the presence of TPMs inhibited them from carrying out their work, but individuals were in the highest agreement. Both groups indicated that the presence of TPMs influenced their decisions to purchase or acquire materials, and again individual researchers were in the highest agreement. These results indicate that TPMs are an even greater inhibiting factor for individuals, perhaps because institutions possess greater resources and have means to access to larger amounts of material. For individuals requiring access to a specific copyright work for research or teaching purposes, the presence of TPMs pose more direct difficulties. Disutility may be more acutely felt by individuals who are the ones using TPM-protected materials, and this is borne out in their greater willingness to seek alternative versions or to avoid purchase. Both groups reported similar levels of agreement that formal mechanisms to request removal of TPMs – either from rightsholders directly or through a government administrative process – would help their work. Since the ability to make such requests from rightsholders already exists in the EU and non-EU jurisdictions surveyed, this suggests that those using them view them positively, but more can be done to make these processes clearer, easier to access, quicker and more widely known to the research community. For institutions, one disadvantage of current systems was their slow response time and cumbersome process. For individuals, the most frequently-cited frustration with existing mechanisms was lack of response from rightsholders and platforms in dealing with their requests.

Statement:	TPMs influence our decision to purchase or acquire material	TPMs inhibit our ability to carry out our work	Ability to request removal of TPMs from rightsholders would help our work	Ability to request removal of TPMs from a government process would help our work
Type				
Institutions	2.12	2.06	2.12	2.12
Individuals	1.40	1.62	2.23	2.21

Table 6: Mean level of agreement by institutions and individuals (lower number indicates greater agreement)

⁹ The Likert-style agreement statements were: (1) agree; (2) somewhat agree; (3) neither agree nor disagree; (4) somewhat disagree; (5) disagree.

5.1 SUMMARY: INDIVIDUAL RESEARCHERS

Individual researchers appear to have different concerns and priorities from the institutions that we surveyed. Geographical restrictions, limits on the ability to reverse-engineer and limits on interoperability were more frequently reported by individual researchers than by institutions. Individuals also accessed a wider range of content types, including more audio-visual media and used different hardware devices than institutions. Individuals attempted to access a wider range of traditional and non-traditional research materials from a broader range of locations and access configurations, which led to blocking in many cases. Privacy concerns were raised by TPMs for many individual researchers. Wishing to remain anonymous or use of a VPN often resulted in access restrictions. Materials and services without TPMs were often more attractive to privacy-conscious users.

In general, individual researchers reported disutility from materials protected by TPMs, preferring in many cases to access and use non-protected materials where possible, including through the use of informal online repositories. Some individuals made requests to rightsholders or engaged with administrative processes in their countries to request removal of TPMs, but users reported these systems being slow and bureaucratically cumbersome. Individual researchers were more willing to circumvent TPMs and more confident in their technical ability to do so, with more than half reporting that they had searched for a means of circumventing a TPM previously, with 50% indicating that they had applied a circumvention technique. Individuals were also more willing to turn to legally ambiguous and pirate sources to access research materials when legal means of access were prevented by TPMs or other digital locks. They reported that such alternative means of access are widespread and easy to access. Individuals reported gaining greater utility from research materials without TPMs because of the ability to manipulate and modify them. University-affiliated and non-affiliated researchers reported broadly similar levels of knowledge of copyright law and experiences with TPMs, indicating that these issues extend beyond institutional boundaries and involve more than lack of copyright knowledge on the part of the individual researcher.

Rodion Kutsaiev / Unsplash

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The strong legal protection afforded to TPMs creates an imbalance in copyright law. While copyright provides incentives for the creation of new works by granting exclusive rights to creators to control the use of their works, the law also balances these incentives with exceptions and limitations to ensure that full beneficial use can be made of copyright-protected materials for the advancement of society, innovation and the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms (Craig, 2010; Geiger, 2013).

If statutory exceptions cannot be enjoyed by beneficiaries due to the presence of TPMs, the economic and social benefits of access built into copyright law are denied to society. This survey has identified specific beneficial uses that are being impeded by TPMs: library lending and access, engaging with the public, research including text-and-data mining, learning and teaching, preservation, innovative uses such as machine learning, and providing for accessibility needs.

Based on the findings of this survey, we make the following recommendations:

- 1/** We support the legal proposals put forward by the DG RTD report (European Commission, 2024) to clarify and improve the legal situation in Europe concerning TPMs. Specifically, we support the proposal to add all research-related copyright exceptions to the list in Article 6(4) InfoSoc Directive, such as the temporary copying exception in Article 5(1) and the quotation right in Article 5(3)(d), both of which may have research and education applications.
- 2/** Our survey research has shown that the use of restrictive contractual terms alongside TPMs can significantly impede enjoyment of copyright exceptions. The DG RTD report recommended “excluding the applicability of subparagraph 4 of Article 6(4) ISD with regard to general research exceptions and other copyright exceptions that may become relevant in research contexts, including Articles 5(1), 5(3)(a), and 5(3)(d) ISD”. (2024: 197). This is important since subparagraph 4 of Article 6(4) Infosoc Directive leaves very little room for interventions when protected content is made available online with agreed contractual terms.
- 3/** Our results show that users and institutions encounter mixed results when making legal requests to rightsholders to request removal of TPMs. Response times vary widely and are often unreasonably long, if a response is received at all. Most libraries and individual researchers we surveyed had not made a legal request. There is no standard format for making such requests across European countries, but instead a patchwork of different national implementations that place varying levels of obligation on rightsholders. We recommend a 72-hour expectation for response from rightsholders as adopted in Bulgaria and Slovenia, with clear steps to be taken if the wait time is exceeded. We also recommend a more robust and transparent processing and reporting system that logs access requests and provides publicly available data on outcomes.

- 4/** Alongside formalisation and harmonisation of systems to make formal access requests, we recommend sector-wide education and skills training to enable researchers and research support institutions to better make use of available legal mechanisms to request removal of TPMs to benefit from copyright exceptions. This could include guides with specific instructions on making requests, similar to the guidance for digital preservation in the USA produced by Albert and Lee (2022). A particular emphasis should be placed on redressing equity gaps identified in this research (e.g. smaller institutions and researchers without institutional support). If administrative processes remain legally opaque or cumbersome, they are likely to exclude these users due to lack of resources and time, leading to low uptake. Education therefore needs to focus on clarification and efficiency.

- 5/** As noted by van der Hoeven et al. (2010), certain national libraries such as France and Germany require that TPM access codes be provided at the point of legal deposit so that institutions can immediately preserve materials (see Erickson & Rodriguez-Perez, 2024). As discussed in Report 3, we recommend that EU policymakers clarify that cultural heritage institutions may circumvent TPMs immediately without needing to approach rightsholders when engaging in preservation as defined under Article 6 CDSM Directive.

7. LIMITATIONS AND DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This report has presented results from our survey of institutions and individual researchers, focusing on EU Member States plus the UK, Norway and Switzerland. We have sought to update and expand the empirical evidence base concerning the impact of TPMs on research, preservation and education. To our knowledge, this is the most detailed survey yet undertaken of European libraries and research institutions focusing on TPMs, although there is significant scope for further research as discussed below.

There are limitations to the present study that offer opportunities for future research. Despite our best efforts, the response rate was higher from institutions and researchers in northern and central Europe, leaving southern and eastern Europe underrepresented in our sample. Institutions from underrepresented regions were also less willing to be contacted for follow-up queries, perhaps due to language barriers. More aggressive purposive sampling of institutions in all 27 Member States would require significantly more resources but could provide a clearer picture of the impact of different national implementations of copyright law on respective research communities. We were able to sample from jurisdictions possessing administrative processes to request access, providing insight into one major way that countries in Europe differ in their treatment of TPMs and exceptions. Due to the nature of the survey method, we were unable to gather deeper insight about specific economic and human resource costs of dealing with TPMs, the proportions of collections impacted, and the number of users prevented from accessing material, a shortcoming that we address in Report 3 on digital preservation costs.¹⁰ That study takes an econometric approach to studying the impact of legacy TPMs on the video game preservation effort to generate quantitative evidence on the costs imposed by TPMs on preservation of digital materials. It is clear from our findings here that TPMs are having a significant impact on institutions and the research community, and deeper economic study of the costs associated with TPMs is recommended to further expand the evidence base and identify workable solutions.

Rothchild (2006) argues that TPMs produce negative externalities that are not sufficiently accounted for in policy. The presence of TPMs leads to a contraction of the public domain (including public access to parts of works carved out via exceptions) with follow-on repercussions for competition, innovation, research and cultural life (2006: 1184). He recommends that the negative externalities imposed by the presence of TPMs be internalised by producers through policy making, to avoid over-production of TPMs and further erosion of the benefits of the public domain.

We recommend that the open knowledge community, researchers, educational institutions and libraries develop systems to track and quantify impacts arising from TPMs, to assist in communicating policy needs. This could include tracking number of users or library items impacted, time delays and costs arising from presence of TPMs preventing lawful uses, and transparency reports of requests made to rightsholders or government processes, including the ultimate outcomes. These systems could be co-designed with academics to improve their robustness as data sources and policy communication tools.

¹⁰ Erickson and Rodriguez Perez (2024). Evidence on Technological Protection Measures: Challenges and social costs in video game preservation. KR 21 Project Report 3.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The evidence suggests that restrictions on legitimate uses of copyrighted works are commonplace for researchers and institutions. Our results indicate that individual researchers are engaging in a wider range of responses to dealing with TPMs than the institutions that support them. Individuals were 3 times more likely to consider circumvention of a TPM on their own and 2.5 times more likely to change providers if their access to content was suspended. Individuals were slightly less confident than institutions in their knowledge about copyright law and exceptions, but they were more confident in their technical ability to circumvent TPMs. This pattern could be explained by the fact that institutions are more sensitive to legal risk and reputational harm (Deazley and Stobo, 2013).

Without a clear means of benefiting from existing exceptions to copyright, and given the disutility of research materials restricted by TPMs and content locks, there is a risk that copyright law's legitimacy could be reduced within the research community. As noted by LIBER (2020), over-protection of materials could lead to an "arms race" between content owners and content seekers, driving lawful users towards other means of accessing content. Our survey results show that these alternative means are readily available and are being used in certain cases. While access to online journals, e-books and databases is a high priority for both institutions and individual researchers, we found that digital content locks and TPMs impact a range of other activities. One important area is preservation of born-digital materials, some of which pre-date the introduction of anti-circumvention prohibitions but may still pose legal risk. These materials include video games, interactive software, electronic records and the operating environments needed to access and view them. Text and image file formats may be inaccessible due to TPMs on legacy devices that support those obsolete formats. There is overlap with the orphan works problem, as publishers of those materials and manufacturers of legacy TPMs may no longer be in business or locatable by institutions. As digital preservation continues to increase as a priority for libraries and archives, balanced and efficient policy responses are required, such as an exception enabling circumvention of obsolete TPMs for purposes of preservation and research (see Albert, 2018; Albert and Lee, 2022).

Rather than grant class-dependent exemptions for specific uses, the approach taken in Europe has been to require beneficiaries of exceptions to make requests to rightsholders. Our research indicates that the current patchwork of different national systems is producing mixed results, with only some institutions and researchers reporting that they have had TPMs successfully removed in a reasonable amount of time. Overall, institutions and individuals indicated that formal legal processes to request removal of TPMs would help their work. These processes should be improved with clear deadlines and alternative routes for achieving access when rightsholders do not respond, as well as removing the requirement for cultural heritage institutions to seek removal of TPMs by rightsholders when engaging in preservation. Furthermore, we encourage harmonisation and systematisation of current approaches, to converge on an efficient solution for researchers, institutions and the public.

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ANNEX 1: SURVEY INSTRUMENT

SURVEY INFORMATION

Project title:

Evidence on Technological Protection Measures: Impact on research, education and preservation

Names of Researchers: Prof Kristofer Erickson, Prof Martin Kretschmer, Dr Victoria Stobo

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The purpose of this research is to explore library and research practices in dealing with Technological Protection Measures (TPMs). TPMs are software or hardware locks that publishers can use to restrict access to copyright materials. TPMS are found in a range of media including e-books, audio-visual formats, online databases and computer games. This research will increase understanding of the impact of TPMs on the professional work of libraries and researchers. It is hoped that the results will inform best practices for research and library practitioners, as well as policy debates focused on access to knowledge. The research is funded by Knowledge Rights 21/ Arcadia– a charitable fund of Lisbet Rausing and Peter Baldwin.

The survey we are conducting seeks insights you have gained in your role as a researcher or library sector practitioner. The questions relate to you and your organisation's activities in respect of Technological protection measures (content locks) and their impact, if any, on your work.

Your participation in the survey is voluntary. You do not need to answer any questions you would prefer not to. The survey should take no longer than approx. 15 mins to complete. **Please note that the submission of your completed survey will constitute your implied consent to take part in the research.** Your response to the survey will be entirely anonymous. Confidentiality will be respected subject to legal constraints and professional guidelines.

- I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
- I understand that other authenticated researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form.
- I acknowledge that any material I provide will be used in accordance with the following:
 - All names and other material likely to identify individuals will be anonymised.
 - The material will be treated as confidential and kept in secure storage at all times.
 - The material will be retained in secure storage for use in future academic research
 - The material may be used in future publications, both print and online.
- I understand that other authenticated researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form.
- I acknowledge the provision of a Privacy Notice in relation to this research project.

Please click the advance button below to begin the survey, or close this browser window to leave the survey.

Q1

Are you responding as an individual or on behalf of an institution (e.g. library)?

- Individual [Logic advances to page 17 of this document]
- Institution [Continue below]

Skip To: End of Block If Are you responding as an individual or on behalf of an institution (e.g. library)? = 1

INSTITUTION:

Q2

What is the estimated number of employees (full-time equivalent) in your institution?

- 1 - 5 (1)
- 6 - 20 (2)
- 21 - 50 (3)
- 51 - 99 (4)
- 100+ (5)

Q3

In which country are you located?

Q4

What type is your institution?

- National Library or Archive (1)
- Public lending library (2)
- Research / University library (3)
- Special collection (4)
- Online archive (5)
- Other: (6) _____

Q5

Do you encounter any of the following types of restrictions?

Please select all that apply.

- Online authentication (e.g. paywalls) (1)
- Limits on access (e.g. total number of access points or quantity viewed) (2)
- Limits on interoperability (e.g. accessing content on different devices) (3)
- Limits on copying (4)
- Limits on downloading (5)
- Limits on printing (6)
- Limits based on geographical location (e.g. geo-blocking) (7)
- Limits on ability to reverse-engineer or repair (8)
- Other: (9) _____

Q6

Has your institution encountered digital content locks on any of the following materials?

- Electronic books (1)
- Electronic journals, magazines or newspapers (2)
- Electronic databases (3)
- Music discs (e.g. CDs) (4)
- Music files (e.g. MP3) (5)
- Music streaming services (6)
- Film / Video discs (e.g. DVDs, Blu-ray) (7)
- Film / Video files (e.g. MP4, AVI) (8)
- Film / Video streaming services (9)
- Video games (10)
- Software (11)
- Photographs, images or maps (12)
- 3D object files (13)
- Materials digitised by the institution (14)
- Hardware devices (15)
- Websites (16)
- Other, please specify: (17) _____

Q7

Has your institution encountered digital content locks on any of the following materials?

	Impeded by content locks (1)	Unsure (2)	Not impeded (3)	Not a function in our institution (4)
Electronic books (1)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronic journals, magazines or newspapers (2)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Electronic databases (3)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Music discs (e.g. CDs) (4)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Music files (e.g. MP3) (5)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Music files (e.g. MP3) (5)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Music streaming services (6)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Film / Video discs (e.g. DVDs, Blu-ray) (7)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Film / Video files (e.g. MP4, AVI) (8)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Film / Video streaming services (9)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Video games (10)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Software (11)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Photographs, images or maps (12)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3D object files (13)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Materials digitised by the institution (14)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hardware devices (15)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Websites (16)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, please specify: (17) _____				

Q8

When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions? Please select all that apply.

- Avoid acquiring or using the material (1)
- Request a refund if materials already acquired (2)
- Seek to acquire alternative version without protection (3)
- Avoid certain uses of the specific work (4)
- Steer users to other formats or options for accessing the material (5)
- Search for means to circumvent the TPMs or content lock to enable access (6)
- Apply circumvention techniques to enable access (7)
- Request publisher / rightsholder to provide access (8)
- Make a request to governmental authority or agency to enable access (9)
- Leave up to the user to acquire by other means (10)
- Other: please specify (11) _____

Display This Question:

If When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions? Please select... = 8

Q9

In the question above, you indicated that you have made a request to a publisher / rightsholder to obtain access to material. Were any of those requests successful?

- Yes (4)
- No (5)
- Other (explain) (6) _____

Display This Question:

If When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions? Please select... = 8

Q10

When making a request to a publisher / rightsholder to provide access, how long did that process take on average?

Display This Question:

If When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions? Please select... = 9

Q11

In the question above, you indicated that you have made a request to a government authority to obtain access to material. Were any of those requests successful?

- Yes (4)
- No (5)

Other (explain) (6)

Display This Question:

If When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions? Please select... = 9

Q12

When making a request to a government authority to provide access, how long did that process take on average?

Q13

When making a formal request to a publisher or government authority to provide access, how long is an acceptable wait time before they should be required to grant access for material you have lawful access to?

	24 hours (1)	72 hours (2)	5 working days (3)	10 working days (4)	1 month (5)	3 months (6)
Publisher (1)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Government (2)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Display This Question:

Has your access to material or subscriptions ever been suspended due to publishers sensing atypic... = 1

Q14

When seeking to circumvent a content lock or TPM, what measures would you consider? Please check all that apply.

- Your own in-house technical expertise (1)
- Your own technical expertise augmented by Internet search (2)
- Third party / outside technical expertise (3)
- Third-party software or tool (4)
- Negotiation with content supplier (5)
- Government or administrative procedure to request rights holders make work available (6)
- Other: please specify (7) _____

Q15

Has your access to material or subscriptions ever been suspended due to publishers sensing atypical activity from your institution? Atypical activity might include repeated computer access requests (e.g. to a publisher's website).

- Yes / Describe reason for suspension of access (optional):
(1) _____
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Has your access to material or subscriptions ever been suspended due to publishers sensing atypic... = 1

Q16

As a result of the suspension, did any of the following occur?

- Provider guaranteed that suspension would not happen again if same issues were to arise (1)
- Institution requested a refund (2)
- A refund or issue of credits was granted (3)
- No refund given (4)
- No meaningful response from provider (5)
- Institution changed behaviour to comply with provider rules (6)
- Institution changed providers or accessed by other means (7)
- Other (please explain): (8) _____

Q17

	Agree (1)	Somewhat agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat disagree (4)	Disagree (5)	Don't know / not applicable (6)
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Please indicate your level of agreement with the statements below.

Our institution is knowledgeable about the law concerning technological protection measures (TPMs). (2)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
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The law concerning what libraries are allowed to do with content protected by TPMs is clear and understandable. (3)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
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The presence of TPMs / content locks factors into our decision to acquire new items, or to take on items in our collection. (4)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
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	Agree (1)	Somewhat agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat disagree (4)	Disagree (5)	Don't know / not applicable (6)
The presence of TPMs / content locks inhibits the ability of our institution to carry out its work. (5)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Our institution feels confident in our technical ability to circumvent TPMs when possible. (6)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We are aware of a legal administrative process in our country to request access to materials protected by TPMs. (7)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The ability to request removal of TPMs by contacting rights holders would help our work. (8)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A government-supported administrative process to request removal of TPMs from specific items would help our work. (9)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q18

Is there anything else you would like to tell use about your experiences with content locks, TPMs or accessing content?

Q19

Would it be alright to contact you to conduct a follow-up interview?

- Yes, you may contact me for a follow-up at the following email address:
(1) _____
- No thanks (2)

Q20

Please select the box below and click "Advance" to submit responses and finish the survey.

- End Survey and submit responses (1)**

Skip To: End of Survey If Please select the box below and click "Advance" to submit responses and finish the survey. = 1

INDIVIDUAL:

Q21

Have you encountered TPMs when doing any of the following?

- Personal recreation (e.g. when consuming content) (1)
- When engaging in personal research or study (2)
- As a student in a learning institution (3)
- As a patron of a library or archive (4)
- As a University-affiliated researcher (5)
- As an entrepreneur or small business owner (6)
- As an employee in a larger business (7)
- As a member of a non-profit or community organisation (8)
- As a professional librarian or archivist (9)
- Other: please specify (10) _____

Q22

In which country are you located?

Q23

**Have you encountered any of the following types of restrictions or content locks?
Please select all that apply.**

- Online authentication (e.g. paywalls) (1)
- Limits on access (e.g. total number of access points or quantity viewed) (2)
- Limits on interoperability (e.g. accessing content on different devices) (3)
- Limits on copying (4)
- Limits on downloading (5)
- Limits on printing (6)
- Limits based on geographic location (e.g. geo-blocking) (7)
- Limits on the ability to reverse engineer or repair (8)
- Other: (9) _____

Other: (10) _____

Q24

Have you encountered digital content locks on any of the following materials?

- Electronic books (1)
- Electronic journals, magazines or newspapers (2)
- Electronic databases (3)
- Music discs (e.g. CDs) (4)
- Music files (e.g. MP3) (5)
- Music streaming services (6)
- Film / Video discs (e.g. DVDs, Blu-ray) (7)
- Film / Video files (e.g. MP4, AVI) (8)
- Film / Video streaming services (9)
- Video games (10)
- Software (11)
- Photographs, images or maps (12)
- 3D object files (13)
- Hardware devices (14)
- Websites (15)
- Other, please specify: (16) _____

Q25

When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions? Please select all that apply.

- Avoid acquiring or using the material (1)
- Request a refund if materials already acquired (2)
- Seek to acquire alternative version without protection (3)
- Avoid certain uses of the specific work (4)
- Search for a different substitute product with similar characteristics (5)
- Search for means to circumvent the TPMs or content lock to enable access (6)
- Apply circumvention techniques to enable access (7)
- Request publisher / rightsholder to provide access (8)
- Make a request to governmental authority or agency to enable access (9)
- Other: please specify (10) _____

Display This Question:

If When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions?

Please select... = 8

Q26

In the question above, you indicated that you have made a request to a publisher / rightsholder to obtain access to material. Were any of those requests successful?

- Yes (4)
- No (5)
- Other (explain): (6) _____

Display This Question:

If When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions?

Please select... = 8

Q27

When making a request to a publisher / rightsholder to provide access, how long did that process take on average?

Display This Question:

When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions? Please select... = 9

Q28

In the question above, you indicated that you have made a request to a government authority to obtain access to material. Were any of those requests successful?

Yes (4)

No (5)

Other (explain): (6) _____

Display This Question:

If When you encounter a content lock or TPM, do you take any of the following actions? Please select... = 9

Q29

When making a request to a government authority to provide access, how long did that process take on average?

Q30

When making a formal request to a publisher or government authority to provide access, how long is an acceptable wait time before they should be required to grant access for material you have lawful access to?

	24 hours (1)	72 hours (2)	5 working days (3)	10 working days (4)	1 month (5)	3 months (6)
Publisher (1)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Government (2)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q31

When seeking to circumvent a content lock or TPM, what measures would you consider? Please check all that apply.

Your own technical expertise (1)

Your own technical expertise augmented by Internet search (2)

Third party / outside technical expertise (3)

- Third-party software or tool (4)
- Request to content supplier (5)
- Government or administrative procedure to request rights holders make work available (6)
- Other: please specify (7) _____

Q32

Has your access to material or subscriptions ever been suspended due to publishers sensing atypical activity from your computer? Atypical activity might include repeated computer access requests (e.g. to a publisher's website).

- Yes / describe reason for suspension of access (optional):
(1) _____
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Has your access to material or subscriptions ever been suspended due to publishers sensing atypic... = 1

Q33

As a result of the suspension, did any of the following occur?

- Provider guaranteed that suspension would not happen again if same issues were to arise (1)
- I requested a refund (2)
- A refund or issue of credits was granted (3)
- No refund given (4)
- No meaningful response from provider (5)
- I changed behaviour to comply with provider rules (6)
- I changed providers or accessed materials by other means (7)
- Other outcome (please explain): (8) _____

Q34

Please indicate your level of agreement with the statements below.

	Agree (1)	Somewhat agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat disagree (4)	Disagree (5)	Don't know / not applicable (6)
I am knowledgeable about Copyright law (1)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am knowledgeable about the law concerning technological protection measures (TPMs). (2)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Agree (1)	Somewhat agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat disagree (4)	Disagree (5)	Don't know / not applicable (6)
The law concerning what individuals are allowed to do with content protected by TPMs is clear and understandable. (3)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The presence of TPMs / content locks impacts my decision to purchase or use material. (4)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The presence of TPMs / content locks inhibits my ability to undertake research or private study (5)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I feel confident in my technical ability to circumvent TPMs when possible. (6)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am aware of a legal administrative process in my country to request access to materials protected by TPMs. (7)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The ability to request removal of TPMs by contacting rights holders would help my work. (8)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A government-supported administrative process to request removal of TPMs from specific items would help my work. (9)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q35

Is there anything else you would like to tell use about your experiences with content locks, TPMs or accessing content?

Q36

Would it be alright to contact you to conduct a follow-up interview?

- Yes, you may contact me for a follow-up at the following email address:
(1) _____
- No thanks (2)

Q37

Please select the box below and click "Advance" to submit responses and finish the survey.

- End Survey and submit responses (1)**

Skip To: End of Survey If Please select the box below and click "Advance" to submit responses and finish the survey. = 1